

Deliverable D1.3

Dissemination, outreach and exploitation plan

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AEGIS-0A

Advancing Diamond
Open Access Publishing

D1.3 Dissemination, outreach and exploitation plan

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Abbreviations

CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EC	European Commission
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
ERA	European Research Area
EUA	European University Association
Eurodoc	European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations
INPOA	Institutional and Non-Profit Open Access
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBER	European Association of Research Libraries
NCC	National Capacity Centre
OA	Open Access
OJS	Open Journals Systems
RFOs	Research Funding Organisations
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
TtT	Train-the-Trainers
UNIC	European University of Post-Industrial Cities
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document presents the AEGIS-OA Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation plan, including the Communication Kit, developed at the early stages of the project to guide communication, dissemination, outreach, engagement, and exploitation activities throughout the project lifecycle and ensure the project's successful implementation.

The purpose of the plan is to define the key stakeholder groups, messaging and channels that will effectively promote the project, its activities, and its results across Europe, while at the same time promoting the broader visibility and understanding of Institutional and Non-Profit Open Access (INPOA) publishing and Diamond Open Access. Recognising the importance of early and continuous stakeholder engagement, the plan additionally presents the results of the stakeholder mapping exercise carried out during the project's initial phase and defines the project's main stakeholder groups, multipliers, and high-level messaging per key stakeholder group. It also identifies the communication, dissemination, outreach, and exploitation channels that will be used to reach the key stakeholder groups, leveraging the existing networks of consortium partners, the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), and aligned external initiatives, projects and organisations that can act as multipliers.

The plan also outlines the activities and events that will support awareness raising, stakeholder engagement, community building, training, dissemination, and exploitation of project results. It also identifies the potential risks for the success of the plan and the project and offers mitigation measures to address them.

Finally, this plan is intended to serve as a living document and will be updated by gathering input and feedback via monitoring mechanisms during the project in Deliverable 1.5 to reflect project developments, stakeholder feedback, and lessons learned.

Introduction

The AEGIS-OA project aims to establish a transparent, sustainable, and high-quality Open Access (OA) scholarly publishing ecosystem in Europe by leveraging and expanding the services of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH). It focuses on integrating open access books alongside journals, upskilling publishing professionals through training programmes, and mobilising the already established network of National Capacity Centres (NCCs), leveraging their influence on the national level, to align efforts and initiatives across borders.

Deliverable 1.3 presents the project's first version of the Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation plan, including a Communication Kit. This deliverable is developed at the start of the project and defines the strategic plan for communication, dissemination, outreach, and exploitation activities. Its objective is to maximise the project's impact by ensuring project awareness, effective stakeholder engagement, wide and targeted dissemination of project results, and the long-term uptake and sustainability of project outputs.

The plan is structured around three strategic pillars:

- Communication and dissemination, to increase visibility of the project and its results.
- Outreach and engagement, to foster impactful interaction, knowledge exchange, and co-creation with stakeholders.
- Exploitation, to support the uptake, reuse, and integration of project results into practice.

The plan builds on the stakeholders identified in the project proposal and further refined during the mapping exercise conducted at the project's Kick-off Meeting (March 2026), which informed the identification of stakeholder groups, multipliers, and tailored engagement approaches for each group. It is aligned with all project Work Packages (WP) supporting coordination (WP1), and enabling stakeholder and community engagement, promoting project outputs, and contributing to the exploitation and sustainability of the results (WP2 - WP6). A central element of the project that is aligned with the plan, is the project's integration within the EDCH environment, where existing services and the EDCH community are leveraged to maximise outreach and the sustainability of AEGIS-OA.

By defining target audiences, key messages, communication channels, activities, and monitoring mechanisms, this plan contributes directly to the achievement of the project's expected impacts. It also addresses potential risks and identifies mitigation strategies to ensure the successful implementation of the plan.

1. Project Stakeholders

1.1. Stakeholder Mapping

A stakeholder mapping workshop was conducted during the AEGIS-OA Kick-off Meeting to identify the main actors that are relevant to and can help realise the project objectives.

The workshop aimed to:

- Identify key stakeholder groups and assess their needs
- Assess stakeholder influence and interest with AEGIS-OA
- Define engagement priorities and approaches
- Identify potential multipliers and collaboration opportunities with other projects and initiatives and organisations.

The stakeholder mapping exercise was repeated at the WP level to identify and prioritise the key stakeholder groups that are most relevant to the separate WPs and Tasks for AEGIS-OA. It also formulated the key messages that would be used by the project and the consortium to engage with and resonate with the key stakeholder groups.

Partners focused on the following eight stakeholder groups (as outlined in the project proposal):

- Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)
- Learned and Scholarly Societies
- Libraries
- National Capacity Centres (NCCs)
- Institutional Non-Profit Open Access (INPOA) publishing services and infrastructure providers
 - For OA Books
 - For OA Journals
- Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)
- National and Institutional policymakers
- Open Access (OA) community

1.2. Key stakeholder groups

Based on the stakeholder mapping and the prioritisation exercises, the consortium identified a set of primary key stakeholder groups and assessed their importance and influence related to the relevance to each of the WPs and their corresponding tasks. The groups identified via this exercise will be prioritised and monitored throughout the project.

It is important to note that some stakeholder groups identified below, for example NCCs, INPOA publishing services, RPOs and libraries may overlap within the same organisations or institutional structures. Through these targeted communication, outreach, and co-creation activities, the project will encourage dialogue and coordination across these groups to help strengthen alignment, harmonise support structures and policies, and foster more connected approaches to Diamond Open Access publishing.

1.2.1. National Capacity Centres (NCCs)

NCCs are a core stakeholder group in AEGIS-OA and play a central role in the implementation, dissemination, uptake, and sustainability of project outcomes of all the WPs at the national level. They serve as the national coordination organisations within the EDCH, supporting alignment between European-level developments and national contexts.

NCCs are a high-priority stakeholder group due to their strategic role in scaling, adapting, and validating project outputs across different countries, languages, and publishing environments on the national level. They are uniquely positioned for ensuring that project results are co-created with communities and are usable, relevant, and effectively integrated into diverse national scholarly publishing systems.

More specifically:

Within WP2, NCCs will play an important role in two areas, first as part of the public consultation of DOAS Version 2.0, which will include book publishing for the first time, and also in validating and supporting the development and uptake of the DOAS¹ (Diamond Open Access Standard) certification framework, ensuring that it can be effectively applied across different national and institutional contexts. This includes supporting the usability, adaptability, and multilingual applicability of additional tools and guidelines that will be created within WP2.

Within WP3, NCCs will contribute by providing regional specific feedback to the design and delivery of training programmes for INPOA publishing trainers, as well as the development of resources and guidelines supporting Diamond OA publishing, including OA books.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/13820036>

Within WP4, NCCs will support the uptake and implementation of tools and services such as the OJS (Open Journal Systems) EDCH preconfiguration package and the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) 2.0. These activities aim to improve the visibility, interoperability,

and discoverability of Diamond OA publishing across Europe.

Within WP5, NCCs represent the core implementation and scaling network of AEGIS-OA and the foundation of the Diamond OA community. They are essential for strengthening national-level engagement and dissemination, supporting DOAS uptake and policy alignment, coordinating national stakeholder communities and reducing fragmentation in Diamond OA efforts across Europe.

Within WP6, NCCs support the broader strategic objective of building a coordinated European network of national centres, focusing on disseminating knowledge and fostering debate about sustainable funding mechanisms.

1.2.2. Institutional Non-Profit Open Access (INPOA) Publishing Services and Infrastructure Providers (OA Journals & OA Books)

INPOA publishing services and infrastructure providers are a AEGIS-OA core stakeholder group as they represent the main actors operating community-led, non-profit Diamond OA publishing services. This group includes OA journal publishers, OA book publishers, and combinations thereof.

This is a core group as they will be directly involved in implementing, testing, and adopting project outputs across certification, training, tools, visibility services, and sustainability mechanisms.

1.2.2.1. INPOA Publishing Services and Infrastructure Providers (OA Journals)

- In WP2, to contribute to the development, validation, and piloting of the DOAS certification framework, ensuring it is applicable to real-world journal publishing practices and workflows. INPOA journal publishers are central to AEGIS-OA activities, particularly in relation to DOAS certification, tools and services, visibility, and funding mechanisms. They will be mobilised in all project WPs and specifically:
- In WP3, to support the design and delivery of a training programme for INPOA publishing trainers.
- In WP4, to test and implement technical solutions developed including the OJS preconfiguration package, as well as inclusion in the DDH to increase discoverability.
- In WP5, to actively join the Diamond OA community and network to increase their discoverability, gain access to community-led tools (EDCH Registry and Forum) and participate in staff development activities.

- In WP6, to participate in consultations on sustainable funding models and mechanisms to support INPOA journal publishing.

1.2.2.2. *INPOA Publishing Services and Infrastructure Providers (OA Books)*

INPOA book publishers are particularly important for AEGIS-OA as it is the first time OA book publishers are included in the EDCH ecosystem and strategically targeted in a European Commission (EC) funded Diamond OA project. They will be mobilised in four project WPs and specifically under the following priorities:

In WP2, they will contribute to the validation of DOAS Version 2.0, which will include criteria for OA book publishing.

In WP3, to participate in the co-development and validation of training materials, resources, and guidelines adapted to OA book publishing.

In WP5, to actively participate in the EDCH Registry and Forum to support visibility and networking opportunities for OA book publishers and to participate in the staff development programmes.

In WP6, to contribute to the discussions on sustainable funding mechanisms for OA book publishing.

1.2.3. Libraries

Libraries are a key priority AEGIS-OA stakeholder group due to their central role in institutional contexts, offering support for Open Access and Open Science, providing institutional publishing services, scholarly communication infrastructures, and Diamond OA publishing practices.

Libraries will be mobilised across several project activities and WPs, particularly in relation to training, visibility, community building, mobility and mentorship, and supporting the sustainability of INPOA publishing.

More specifically:

Within WP3, libraries will be consulted for the development and promotion of training programmes, resources, guidelines, and materials supporting OA publishing professionals and Diamond OA publishing practices, including activities related to OA books publishing.

Within WP4, libraries will be engaged in activities aimed at increasing the visibility and discoverability of Diamond OA journals through the DDH and related indexing services.

Libraries will also play an important role in WP5 activities related to onboarding organisations to the EDCH Registry, actively engaging with the EDCH Forum, strengthening the NCCs network, and supporting mobility, staff exchange and mentorship initiatives for Diamond OA publishing professionals across Europe.

Finally, libraries are also recognised as a key stakeholder group for WP6 and specifically Task 6.2 related to aligning, scaling, and expanding sustainable funding mechanisms for INPOA publishing. Libraries will be invited to contribute to a Diamond OA sustainability framework, ensuring adoption and long-term impact of project outcomes.

1.2.4. Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)

Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) are an important stakeholder group for AEGIS-OA, particularly in relation to WP6 focusing on the sustainability and pooling of resources,

RPOs play an important role in supporting institutional publishing services, Open Science strategies, and Diamond OA initiatives. Within the project, they are especially relevant to Task 6.2, which focuses on expanding and aligning existing funding mechanisms for INPOA journal publishing across Europe, and Task 5.1, which focuses on growing the EDCH Registry.

1.2.5. Open Access (OA) community

The broader OA community will also play a key role within AEGIS-OA, as it represents the wider ecosystem of researchers, publishers, service providers, infrastructures, initiatives involved in non-profit, community-led scholarly publishing, and Open Access and Open Science. The project will interact with the broader community via communication and dissemination activities and where relevant co-creation and consultation activities to strengthen the infrastructure for Open Access and Open Science.

The OA community is engaged across multiple WPs:

- In WP2, to provide feedback, and support the broader uptake of the DOAS framework. The community will play an important role in validating quality standards for Diamond OA publishing services, contributing to the wider trust and adoption.
- In WP3, by participating in training activities, and contributing to the development of useful resources, including the development of guidelines and tools for Diamond OA book and journal publishing.
- In WP4, by engaging with tools and technologies built, including DDH 2.0 and related indexing and visibility tools that improve the interoperability and discoverability of Diamond OA outputs.

- In WP5, by participating in community-building activities, including onboarding to the Registry and Forum and involvement in networking and knowledge exchange initiatives.
- For WP6, the OA Community can provide expertise and experience, and convene and mobilise many stakeholders to help sustain Diamond OA and disseminate the WP main output.

1.2.6. Learned and Scholarly Societies

Scholarly societies represent an important stakeholder group within AEGIS-OA due to their strong inter-disciplinary reach and their central role in community-led scholarly publishing and research dissemination.

The project will engage with scholarly societies particularly through activities related to WP5 and the development and onboarding of the EDCH Registry and Forum under Task 5.1. These activities aim to strengthen collaboration, networking, and visibility across the Diamond OA ecosystem.

1.2.7. Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) are an important stakeholder group for AEGIS-OA, especially for WP6 and Task 6.3, which focuses on developing mechanisms for RFOs to support INPOA publishing.

RFOs play a strategic role in shaping Open Science policies, funding priorities, and long-term sustainability approaches for scholarly publishing. They are considered a high-priority stakeholder group for the project due to their potential to support and scale sustainable funding models for Institutional and INPOA publishing.

1.2.8. National, International and Institutional policymakers

National and institutional policy makers are recognised as an important stakeholder group within AEGIS-OA, particularly for WP2 and Tasks T2.3 and T2.4, for the development of the DOAS certification and the DOAS Observatory to provide evidence-based input that can inform policy development, and funding conditions across Europe. National policy makers are closely related to the RFOs but AEGIS-OA will engage with both groups via targeted actions related to policy alignment and framework sustainability across WP2 and WP6.

National policy makers are also identified as an important stakeholder group for WP6. The main WP output will indeed also address national Diamond OA funding mechanisms.

In addition, AEGIS-OA also recognises the importance of engaging with European and international policymakers and initiatives working in the areas of Open Science, scholarly communication, and Diamond OA. Relevant European and international organisations, including the European Commission (EC), UNESCO² (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization), and CoNOSC³ (Council for National Open Science Coordination) contributes to strengthening alignment between national and international approaches, increasing the visibility of project results, and supporting broader policy uptake and sustainability of Diamond OA frameworks and recommendations.

1.3. The multiplier approach

In addition to the primary key stakeholder groups identified above, beyond the strong partnership of the project which represents expertise in institutional publishing, diamond open access, and open science, AEGIS-OA will engage with the wider Diamond OA ecosystem, including highly relevant projects, initiatives and organisations that can support and multiply the visibility and uptake of project activities and results. These multipliers can be defined as the groups that have both the capacity and the reach to further disseminate the project's messages, activities and results beyond the direct stakeholder groups through their own established networks and channels.

The project will work closely with multipliers at European, national, and also international levels to ensure the broader outreach and engagement, cross-pollination and avoiding duplication of work. These include but are not limited to, UNESCO, the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access,⁴ the Diamond OA Summits, the latest instalment of which has created the Bengaluru Roadmap and Action Plan on Diamond Open Access (2026),⁵ the ALMASI project,⁶ and various other stakeholders in Africa (AJOL), Latin America (Redalyc-Amelica), Indonesia (Relawan Jurnal), South Korea (KISTI) and Canada (Erudit, coalition PubliCA).

1.3.1. EDCH

The EDCH itself represents a major multiplier for AEGIS-OA. Using its already established and well connected network and channels, the project maximises its

²<https://www.unesco.org/en>

³<https://conosc.org/>

⁴<https://scienceeurope.org/our-resources/action-plan-for-diamond-open-access/>

⁵<https://zenodo.org/records/20168763>

⁶<https://almasiproject.org>

potential and reach and starts on a strong foundation for the successful implementation and delivery of its results.

1.3.2. Other Diamond OA, scholarly publishing and Open Science projects

Other European and international projects working on Diamond OA, and scholarly publishing, represent important multipliers for AEGIS-OA. Collaboration with such projects, like ALMASI, enables knowledge exchange, cross-dissemination of results, and cross-pollination of communities across the wider scholarly publishing ecosystem in Europe and beyond. These collaborations help avoid the duplication of effort while increasing the visibility, reach, and potential uptake of project outputs.

1.3.3. Aligned initiatives

Aligned initiatives and policy frameworks such as the Barcelona Declaration⁷ act as strategic multipliers by supporting the visibility and policy relevance of AEGIS-OA outcomes. Engagement with these initiatives helps position project results within broader discussions on Open Science, research assessment, and responsible scholarly communication. These collaborations also support the dissemination of project activities and results to policymakers, funders, RPOs and RFOs, contributing to reaching these identified key stakeholder groups.

1.3.4. University associations and Alliances

University associations and Alliances⁸, like the European University Association (EUA),⁹ Enlight¹⁰, The Guild¹¹ and the European University of Post-Industrial Cities (UNIC)¹² represent important multiplier groups for AEGIS-OA due to their broad institutional reach and their role in shaping strategic priorities related to Open Access, scholarly publishing and Open Science. Through their established networks and communities, these alliances can support the dissemination and promotion of relevant project activities, tools, and recommendations, to their member universities and research-performing organisations.

⁷ <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>

⁸

<https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/european-universities-initiative/map>

⁹ <https://eua.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://enlight-eu.org>

¹¹ <https://www.the-guild.eu>

¹² <https://unic.eu/en>

1.3.5. Researcher networks and communities

Researcher networks and communities represent a key multiplier for AEGIS-OA, as researchers are the end users and practitioners of scholarly publishing services in diverse roles including authors, editors, reviewers, and members of editorial boards. Networks such as the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc)¹³, Young European Research Universities Network (YERUN)¹⁴ and the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA)¹⁵ can support the dissemination of project activities and contribute to strengthening awareness, trust, and adoption of community-led Diamond Open Access publishing practices.

1.3.6. Library associations

Library associations, like the European Association of Research Libraries¹⁶ (LIBER) and the International Federation of Library Associations¹⁷ (IFLA) are key multiplier organisations for AEGIS-OA due to their strong national and international networks of academic and research libraries, as well as their established role supporting Open Access and Open Science, scholarly communication, and offering institutional publishing support. They are well positioned to support the dissemination of project results, tools, guidelines, and training materials to libraries.

1.4. High level messaging per stakeholder group

To successfully reach these identified influential and interested stakeholder groups, AEGIS-OA has defined the following high-level messages that are tailored to each group to ensure consistency and alignment across the project's consortium.

These messages reflect the specific role of each group within the project based on the mapping and prioritisation exercise outlined above, and their expected contribution, and the value they derive from participation. This initial definition of the messages is not intended as an exhaustive list but rather as a starting point for project work. It is expected that this initial messaging will be updated and refined as the project progresses and the first results are produced.

¹³ <https://www.eurodoc.net/>

¹⁴ <https://yerun.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://www.mariecuriealumni.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://libereurope.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://www.ifla.org/>

Key stakeholder group	Targeted messaging
National Capacity Centres (NCCs)	AEGIS-OA enables and empowers NCCs to serve as the national coordination bodies for Diamond OA leading the transition in their respective countries, supporting the scaling and adaptation of tools, training, and frameworks to ensure alignment between European and national ecosystems.
Libraries	AEGIS-OA supports libraries in their role as key scholarly communication and institutional publishing actors by providing them with the tools, training, and frameworks that strengthen their services and Diamond OA infrastructures.
INPOA Publishing Services and Infrastructure Providers (OA Journals)	AEGIS-OA supports INPOA journal publishers in improving the quality, visibility, interoperability, and sustainability of Diamond OA journals by providing certification, technical tools, training, and services that enhance journal visibility, recognition and long-term sustainability.
INPOA Publishing Services and Infrastructure Providers (OA Books)	AEGIS-OA supports INPOA book publishers in adapting existing quality frameworks to OA books, strengthening their visibility, and improving the sustainability of Diamond OA books through tailored certification frameworks, training resources, and community developed tools and guidelines.
Open Access (OA) community	AEGIS-OA engages and works with the OA community to strengthen trust, adoption and sustainability of community-led publishing, by enabling their active participation, feedback, and co-creation of project outputs.
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	AEGIS-OA supports RPOs in strengthening sustainable, interoperable,

	and community-driven institutional publishing services by providing frameworks and evidence to support institutional decision-making and the value of investing in Diamond OA.
Learned and Scholarly Societies	AEGIS-0A strengthens community-led scholarly publishing by supporting learned and scholarly societies in sustaining and developing Diamond OA models, while improving collaboration, visibility, training, and services that enhance journal recognition, long-term sustainability, and disciplinary engagement across Europe.
Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	AEGIS-0A supports RFOs in further developing coherent and sustainable funding mechanisms for non-profit Open Access publishing, by aligning, scaling up and expanding existing funding mechanisms.
National, International and Institutional policymakers	AEGIS-0A provides policymakers with evidence-based frameworks and shared reference models to support the definition of coherent Diamond OA policies, reducing fragmentation and aligning national and European strategies as well as contributing to the sustainability of Diamond OA.

Table 1: High level messaging per key stakeholder group for AEGIS-0A.

2. Communication & Dissemination

The communication and dissemination activities of AEGIS-OA aim to maximise the visibility, reach, and impact of the project throughout its lifecycle and beyond. The project adopts a community-oriented and stakeholder-driven approach to its communication and dissemination plan, ensuring that activities are aligned with the needs of the Diamond OA community.

These activities will support awareness-raising around the project's objectives and results, while also promoting broader understanding of INPOA publishing and the importance of Diamond OA.

Communication and dissemination efforts will build on existing networks, services, and channels of the EDCH, and of consortium partners' channels and networks to ensure broad outreach and long-term impact of the project.

2.1. Communication & dissemination objectives

The communication and dissemination activities of AEGIS-OA have the following objectives to:

- Increase the visibility and impact of the AEGIS-OA project at the European and international level
- Raise awareness of Diamond OA and INPOA publishing models highlighting the importance of Diamond OA books
- Promote project services, activities, tools, and results
- Building awareness and the sense of community around the project objectives and planned activities early on via introductory presentations and webinars
- Strengthen the visibility and positioning of the EDCH as a central coordination point and a platform for the project and more broadly for Diamond OA publishing in Europe.

Communication and dissemination activities will follow the principles of openness, accessibility, inclusiveness, and multilingual outreach whenever possible. This includes, for example, the use of open licenses for publicly available materials, the use of open-source software and platforms where appropriate, the provision of accessible communication formats and materials, and collaboration with the NCC network to support multilingual communication and adaptation of materials to different national contexts.

The project communication approach is also aligned with the two overarching phases of the project:

Figure 1: The AEGIS-OA Methodology

Phase 1 – Co-creation and development

During the first months of the project, communication and dissemination activities will focus on:

- Introducing the project and its objectives
- Raising awareness about the project among key stakeholder groups
- Supporting stakeholder mapping and community building
- Promoting relevant AEGIS-OA and external events including webinars, workshops, and training activities
- Establishing project communication channels and visual identity

Phase 2 – Integration and implementation

During the second phase, communication and dissemination activities will increasingly focus on:

- Dissemination of project results and outputs as they become finalised
- Promotion of training, mobility and mentorship opportunities and co-creation activities
- Showcasing success stories and community practices from across the Diamond OA community
- Encouraging the uptake and reuse of project outputs and results via broad communication and dissemination

2.2. Communication kit

To support coherent, and effective communication activities across the project consortium, AEGIS-OA has developed a Communication Kit during the initial phase of the project. This Kit provides partners with practical guidance on the AEGIS-OA brand, dedicated templates and materials to support the communication, outreach and engagement activities throughout the project.

The Communication Kit aims to:

- Ensure consistency in the visual identity of the project
- Facilitate the communication and dissemination activities across the consortium
- Support all partners in promoting project activities and results via their own organisational channels and networks
- Strengthen the visibility of the project and its connection to the EDCH.

The Communication Kit¹⁸ includes the following:

- Project logo variations
- Branding guidelines¹⁹
- Project-branded presentation templates (See Appendix A)
- Project-branded document templates (See Appendix A)
- Project-branded social media templates (See Appendix A)

The AEGIS-OA brand is strongly aligned with the EDCH one to support the better integration of project materials and results within the already existing EDCH environment. All materials produced and included in the Kit can be found in Appendix A.

The Kit will be updated throughout the project's lifecycle, and additional materials will be added to enrich it, based on the evolving stakeholder needs and priorities.

2.3. Communication channels

AEGIS-OA will, above all, build on and leverage the existing communication and dissemination channels, networks, and communities of the EDCH and the consortium partners. The project will combine centralised European-level communication with

¹⁸ <https://edch.eu/aegis-oa/communication-kit>

¹⁹ <https://edch.eu/sites/default/files/AEGIS-OA/Brand%20Guidelines/AEGIS-OA%20Brand%20Guidelines.pdf>

decentralised national and community-based dissemination approaches to maximise outreach, and uptake of project activities and results across borders.

The communication channels will support awareness-raising, dissemination of project outputs, promotion of events and training activities, and long-term integration of project results into the EDCH.

2.3.1. EDCH Channels

The EDCH will serve as a central communication and dissemination hub for AEGIS-OA, ensuring visibility and accessibility of project activities, services, tools, and results for the European Diamond OA community.

2.3.1.1. *AEGIS-OA Webpage on the EDCH Website*

The AEGIS-OA project webpage²⁰ is part of the EDCH website and serves as the central online entry point for all project-related communication, dissemination, and outreach activities. The webpage acts as a dedicated hub where stakeholders can access up-to-date information about the project's objectives, activities, events, outputs, and opportunities for participation.

²⁰ <https://edch.eu/aegis-oa/>

AEGIS-OA

Advancing Diamond
Open Access Publishing

D1.3 Dissemination, outreach and exploitation plan

Figure 2: The AEGIS-OA webpage on the EDCH Website

The integration of the AEGIS-OA webpage into the already established EDCH website reflects the project's strategic alignment with the EDCH and reinforces the long-term sustainability and the seamless integration of project results into the EDCH. By embedding the project within the existing EDCH infrastructure, AEGIS-OA benefits from the already established European Diamond OA community, and its communication channels.

The webpage will evolve throughout the project lifecycle and progressively integrate project outputs and services into the broader EDCH environment, ensuring continuity, discoverability, and long-term access to AEGIS-OA results.

2.3.1.2. EDCH Registry and Forum²¹

The EDCH Registry and Forum are designed to foster collaboration and networking among Diamond OA Publishers, Service Providers, and Tools and Technology Providers in Europe. The Registry is designed to present and promote Diamond OA organisations, highlighting their expertise, services, and operational capacities. The

²¹ Registry: <https://registry.edch.eu/>
Forum: <https://forum.edch.eu/>

Forum provides the space for the European Diamond OA community to share their experiences, exchange information, raise issues, and collaboratively solve them. AEGIS-OA will also leverage this powerful network to reach out to the community and share project news related to its progress, results and upcoming events. The EDCH Registry and Forum provide the platform for a multilingual and multicultural approach to mitigate any potential barriers and provide a great opportunity to reach out to the diverse communities within Diamond OA.

2.3.1.3. *EDCH Social Media*

AEGIS-OA will use the main social media channels of the EDCH to support the communication, dissemination, outreach, and engagement activities of the project. Similar to the AEGIS-OA webpage, this approach ensures strong alignment between the project and the broader EDCH ecosystem while maximising visibility within the already established EDCH follower base.

The project will use the EDCH social media accounts on:

- LinkedIn²²
- Bluesky²³

LinkedIn will be used as a channel to primarily target all identified stakeholder groups, with tailored messaging and tagging as appropriate.

Bluesky will be used to support the reach of the broader Open Access and Open Science and scholarly communication communities.

2.3.2. *Partner Channels*

In addition to the main EDCH communication channels, AEGIS-OA will encourage partners to actively contribute to the wider dissemination and outreach of the project's activities by utilising their own institutional and national communication channels. Consortium partners represent a unique and diverse range of organisations connected to scholarly publishing, open access experts, research infrastructures, RPOs and their libraries, policymakers, funders, and training communities across Europe. This provides great dissemination and outreach opportunities.

The following partner channels will be used throughout the project (this is an indicative list and might change throughout the project's lifecycle):

- Institutional websites and project pages
- Institutional newsletters and mailing lists

²² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eudch>

²³ <https://bsky.app/profile/eudch.bsky.social>

- Social media channels (e.g., LinkedIn, Bluesky, Mastodon, Facebook)
- Conferences, workshops, webinars, and external events
- Blogs or news services managed by AEGIS-OA partners.

To leverage these channels, an internal tracking list has been created, including partner-controlled channels and external mailing lists and other channels, on the national and European level to promote AEGIS-OA progress and results. Social media presence will be coordinated with consortium partners and NCCs to maximise reach and encourage a successful snowball effect for impact through further dissemination across partner and community networks

3. Outreach & Engagement

The outreach and engagement activities of AEGIS-OA aim to foster the active participation, collaboration, and knowledge exchange across the key stakeholder groups and the broader European Diamond OA community. To maximise the impact and ensure the relevance and success of the project results, AEGIS-OA will leverage the powerful network of the project partners, the NCCs and the EDCH Registry and Forum members. This will help ensure that relevant and national Diamond OA communities and organisations are actively involved in the co-creation, validation, uptake, and long-term sustainability of project outputs.

Outreach and engagement activities will support the development of stronger connections between the project, the EDCH and the wider Diamond OA and Open Access communities. Particular emphasis will be placed on building sustainable relationships with the key stakeholder groups, strengthening national and European networks, and encouraging active participation in project activities, events, and training.

3.1. Outreach & Engagement objectives

The outreach and engagement activities of AEGIS-OA have the following objectives:

- Co-creating the key project activities and outputs
- Maximising the project's impact by establishing a well-connected European network for INPOA publishing
- Supporting the onboarding and participation of organisations and individuals in the EDCH Registry & Forum
- Organising and participating in events to promote the project and liaise, discuss and listen to the Diamond OA community
- Strengthening collaboration and exchange through the NCCs network
- Strengthening national and European coordination around Diamond OA publishing
- Contributing to the long-term sustainability of Diamond OA and the integration of project results within the EDCH specifically.

Similar to the communication and dissemination objectives, the project's outreach and engagement approach will also be aligned with the two overarching phases of the project:

Phase 1 – Co-creation and development

During the first months of the project, outreach and engagement activities will focus on:

- Establishing or reinforcing existing relationships with the key stakeholder groups via targeted invitations and tailored events
- Strengthening collaboration with NCCs and existing Diamond OA communities through organising community-led events including, AEGIS-OA workshops, consultations and meetings
- Supporting stakeholder participation in project activities, including training, workshops, consultations, and co-creation activities via tailored approaches to dissemination
- Supporting onboarding and developing community participation within the EDCH Registry and Forum, through awareness and advocacy campaigns, training, staff exchange and mentorship programmes.

Phase 2 – Integration and implementation

During the second phase, outreach and engagement activities will increasingly focus on:

- Strengthening stakeholder participation through targeted WP co-creation planning and actions in implementation activities
- Supporting uptake and reuse by promoting outputs as openly licensed and/or educational resources
- Promoting and encouraging participation in the AEGIS-OA training and capacity-building activities through targeted stakeholder invitations
- Supporting long-term sustainability and community ownership of project results via integrating into the EDCH
- Encouraging and supporting policy dialogue amongst RPOs and RFOs and coordinating alignment around Diamond OA publishing
- Participating and presenting AEGIS-OA in strategic events across scholarly publishing and Diamond OA ecosystems

3.2. Events

AEGIS-OA organised events and participation in external events will play a central role in the communication, dissemination, outreach, and exploitation plan of AEGIS-OA. Through a combination of project-led events and representation of the project in

external events, the consortium aims to maximise the visibility, uptake, and long-term impact of project results across the European Diamond OA ecosystem.

3.2.1. AEGIS-OA events

Event	Timing	Stakeholder Group(s)	Purpose	Related WP(s)
1st Diamond OA Festival (online)	February 2027	All key stakeholder groups	The AEGIS-OA flagship event aims to strengthen and develop ties with the European Diamond OA community	All WPs
2nd Diamond OA Festival & final conference (in-person)	February 2028	All key stakeholder groups	The AEGIS-OA flagship event aims to strengthen and develop ties with the European Diamond OA community & will present the project's final results	All WPs
3 Awareness-raising webinars	Organised in the first year of the project	Focusing on targeting different key stakeholder groups	Introduce the project to a wider audience	All WPs
10 Outreach and Training Webinars	Throughout the 24-month project duration	INPOA publishers, RPOs, RFOs, libraries, OA community	Dissemination of project results, training and outreach	All WPs
Public Consultation and Validation Event for DOAS	September-November 2026	INPOA publishers	To present, co-create, and validate the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) adaptations for books	WP2
National Capacity Centres (NCC)	3 times per year	National Capacity Centres	To encourage alignment, coordination and	WP5

Online Meetings			assess stakeholder needs	
Workshop on DOAS and Books	May 2027	INPOA book publishers, National Capacity Centres	To discuss and promote DOAS for books in national contexts	WP5
Research Performing Organisation (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisation (RFOs) Meetings	2 meetings organised by February 2028	Representatives of RPOs and RFOs involved in INPOA publishing funding	To contribute to the development of a multi-level and multi-stakeholder framework to financially support INPOA publishing and outline the role of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)	WP6

Table 2: AEGIS-OA Events

3.2.2. External Events

Across the project's lifecycle, AEGIS-OA will be presented in key events to reach the identified key stakeholder groups and ensure the visibility and impact of the project's progress and results. The table below outlines upcoming events that have been indicated by project partners as being highly relevant for the project. All partners will make concrete efforts to represent AEGIS-OA and attend some of these events, depending on funding opportunities. The list of events will be updated throughout the project.

Event	Date	Location	Link
COAR Annual Conference 2026	1-3 June 2026	Braga, Portugal	https://coar-repositories.org/topic/annual-meetings/
PUBMET 2026	9-11 September	Zadar, Croatia	https://pubmet.hr/
OASPA Conference 2026	21-23 September 2026	Zagreb, Croatia	https://www.oaspa.org/events/annualconference/

ConfOA (Lusophone Open Science Conference)	6-9 October 2026	Faro, Portugal	https://confoa.rcaap.pt/2026/
UKSG 2027	5-7 April 2027	Glasgow, Scotland	https://www.uksg.org/annualconference/uksg-2027-call-for-topics-submission-form/
Munin Conference 2027	20-22 April 2027	Tromsø, Norway	https://site.uit.no/muninconf/
AEUP Meeting 2027	May 2027	TBC	https://coar-repositories.org/topic/annual-meetings/
Open Repositories 2027	6-10 June 2027	Salvador, Brazil	https://www.openrepositories.org/
LIBER 2027	TBC	TBC	https://liberconference.eu/
Open Science Fair (OS Fair) 2027	TBC	TBC	https://www.opensciencefair.eu/
PUBMET 2027	TBC	TBC	https://pubmet.hr/
4th Diamond OA Summit	December 2027	Bali, Indonesia	https://www.diamondsummit.org/

Table 3: Indicative list of external events relevant for AEGIS-0A

3.3. Training

Training plays a crucial role in advancing AEGIS-0A's outreach and engagement objectives. It acts as both a catalyst for community building and a means of enabling co-creation and the exchange of experiences. Through structured learning opportunities, such as workshops and hands-on sessions, training activities help

participants develop shared understandings, align practices, and strengthen their sense of belonging within the European Diamond OA community. The Train the Trainers (TtT, Task 3.1) will provide concrete spaces where institutions, NCCs, and other stakeholders can collectively explore challenges, share insights, and co-design practical solutions, reinforcing collaboration and mutual trust across the network.

In the early co-creation and development phase, training will introduce participants to the project's vision and tools. This helps establish a common foundation and encourages early engagement. The community has been invited to take part in the TtT development from its early stages. In the integration and implementation phase, training serves to embed project outputs into practice, support uptake of AEGIS-OA results, including those about books, and ensure long-term sustainability by integrating them into EDCH services such as Resources and the Training platform.²⁴ By promoting continuous learning and peer exchange, training ensures that outreach efforts lead not only to awareness but also to empowered, connected communities capable of sustaining and advancing Diamond OA principles across Europe. To encourage a broad participation and accessibility, project partners will strive to provide multilingual resources and organise dedicated activities where possible.

3.4. Community-building via the EDCH

Community-building directly supports the project's objective of strengthening and connecting the fragmented Diamond OA landscape across the European Research Area and helps maximise project impact. In the context of the EDCH, community-building is framed as central to the sustainability of Diamond OA publishing and a way to strengthen connections and foster partnerships within the Diamond OA landscape in Europe. One of the EDCH's dedicated Task Forces is specifically focused on community-building and it is also responsible for coordinating NCCs and EDCH Advocates. This task force will actively support project activities, mainly in WP5.

The project will adopt a two-way community engagement approach, relying on already established and active communities as ambassadors and advocates while also building new communities around the EDCH Registry, Forum, and related services.

The project will also develop a pilot framework (T5.3) for the exchange of publishing specialists across Europe (connecting mentors and mentees, a directory of host institutions for exchanges). It will facilitate easier access to Erasmus+ mobility funds

²⁴ Resources: <https://resources.edch.eu/>
Training platform: <https://training.edch.eu/>

for INPOA publishing professionals and build partnerships with university alliances (e.g., Enlight, the Guild) to help sustain the community beyond the project duration. Members of the existing network of NCCs and EDCH Advocates will serve as local contact points, improving outreach and helping connect local communities to the broader European network.

3.4.1. Registry & Forum

Through the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), and in particular through the EDCH Registry and Forum, the project will foster collaboration, visibility, and knowledge exchange among Diamond OA publishers, service providers, tools and technology providers, scholarly societies, and policymakers. Community-engagement activities will contribute directly to the communication and dissemination objectives of AEGIS-OA by increasing the visibility and positioning of the EDCH as a central coordination and support hub for Diamond OA publishing in Europe. Task 5.1 “Expand the EDCH Community via its Registry & Forum service” seeks to widen the community through dedicated campaigns encouraging the onboarding of INPOA publishing organisations in the EDCH Registry, with a special focus on the publishers of Diamond OA books. Particular attention will also be given to the integration of learned and scholarly societies through targeted scoping activities based on the Directory of Learned Societies and dedicated campaigns encouraging their registration in the Registry.

The EDCH Forum will support community-building activities by providing dedicated discussion spaces, including a specific Forum category for INPOA Books. The Forum’s profile management functionalities will enable the creation of a directory of publishing professionals interested in collaboration and mobility opportunities. Multilingual support will be ensured in the EDCH Forum in order to maximise accessibility and inclusiveness.

3.4.2. NCCs

The National Capacity Centres Network (NCCN) will constitute a key pillar of the AEGIS-OA community-building strategy by strengthening coordination and capacity-building activities at the national level and across the European Research Area. Through Task 5.2 “National Capacity Centres Network (NCCN)”, the project will identify, support, and connect NCCs supporting INPOA publishing services. The NCCN will facilitate exchanges among stakeholders working on Diamond OA publishing infrastructures, policies, training, and certification, and will also promote the uptake of project outputs within and across countries.

The network will develop a common action plan addressing key areas such as DOAS certification and monitoring, translation and localisation of the DOAS framework and self-assessment tools, training and capacity-building, national research assessment systems, and Open Science (OS) policies. Regular coordination will help reduce fragmentation across national Diamond OA landscapes and strengthen collaboration between institutional, national, and European initiatives. To support this work, the project will organise three online meetings per year with NCC representatives, as well as annual in-person meetings during the European Diamond OA Festival.

NCCs will support outreach for the EDCH Registry by identifying and engaging national stakeholder communities. They will also contribute to the development of a directory of INPOA publishing professionals and a pilot framework for mobility and cooperation opportunities across Europe.

The project will also strengthen the integration of the European Diamond OA Books Community within the NCCN framework. In collaboration with NCCs, national book platform initiatives, institutional capacity centres, and groups such as the Open Access Books Network, the project will promote the use of DOAS among book publishers and support the integration of book-focused stakeholders into the EDCH Registry and Forum.

3.4.3. Advocacy campaign

Within WP5, NCCN will be tasked with developing an advocacy campaign aimed at promoting the inclusion of INPOA publishing outputs, including those hosted in the DDH, within national research assessment frameworks and Open Science policies. The NCC network will also collaborate with national chapters of Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) to advance the recognition of INPOA publishing in national research assessment systems and encourage the establishment of dedicated CoARA Working Groups focused on this objective.

4. Exploitation and Sustainability

4.1. Exploitation & Sustainability Objectives

The exploitation and sustainability objectives of AEGIS-OA aim to ensure that project results are effectively taken up, reused, and integrated beyond the project lifetime, contributing to a long-term and sustainable Diamond Open Access ecosystem in Europe.

A key element of the exploitation and sustainability plan is the integration of AEGIS-OA results into the EDCH. The EDCH acts as the hub for coordination, service provision, and community engagement for Diamond Open Access publishing in Europe and will integrate all project results.

The project outputs, including the DOAS certification framework, training materials, resources and guidelines materials, are being embedded and integrated into EDCH services and workflows by design rather than remaining standalone project deliverables.

4.2. Key Exploitable Results

The following Key Exploitable Results (KERs) present the list of AEGIS-OA results expected to support the long-term uptake, sustainability, and impact of the project outcomes within the Diamond OA ecosystem.

These KERs represent the project's current priorities and anticipated outputs. As the project progresses, they will be further refined and validated through stakeholder engagement, co-creation activities, and implementation across the different WPs. An update on the final list will be included in the updated version of this plan in Deliverable 1.5.

4.2.1. DOAS adaptation for INPOA book publishers

Innovation

The DOAS adaptation for INPOA book publishers will create a new version of DOAS. Version 2.0 of DOAS will integrate books into the existing DOAS items. The seven core components of DOAS and the subheadings will not be changed in version 2.0. However, existing items will be edited where necessary and new items will be written to make DOAS relevant to both journal and book publishers who publish Diamond OA content.

This will allow INPOA book publishers to follow a specific set of items within DOAS that are relevant to book publishing.

Exploitation

Stakeholder groups

The primary stakeholder groups for the DOAS adaptation for book publishers are:

- INPOA publishing services that publish Diamond OA books via the standard, the resources and ultimately through certification
- National Capacity Centres (NCCs) as main implementers at the national level.
- Institutional publishing infrastructures as promoters of the process.
- RPOs and RFOs as institutional actors.
- The Diamond OA community.

Dissemination channels

- Publication of DOAS Version 2.0 on the EDCH and the project website.
- Community engagement through NCCs' network, in the first instance through the public consultation and validation event and then as part of the workshop for Diamond OA books with NCCs.
- Presentation and demonstration at Diamond OA events, conferences, and community webinars.
- Outreach campaigns through the EDCH Forum.
- Promotion via partner institutional channels: Newsletters, social media, etc
- Collaboration with aligned initiatives (like ALMASI), to maximise reach.

Partner contribution

The OAPEN Foundation, as task lead, will coordinate the promotion of the book's adaptation, FECYT will coordinate the wider promotion of DOAS Version 2.0 and the translations of DOAS. Project partners will also contribute to the promotion of DOAS Version 2.0.

NCCs will act as the primary vehicle for national-level implementation, helping in the adoption of DOAS Version 2.0 for INPOA book publishers.

Sustainability

Maintenance

The DOAS adaptation for INPOA book publishers will be maintained in the long term through its integration into EDCH services.

The NCCs network will provide support for the ongoing review and for the maintenance of the standard at the national level, while periodic updates will be coordinated to ensure criteria remain aligned with the evolving requirements of Diamond OA publishing.

Integration

The DOAS adaptation for books will be embedded into the EDCH ecosystem, ensuring it serves as a central reference point. The version derived from this task will be integrated into the DOAS Certification Framework to provide the same structured quality assessment workflow for books and for journal publishers.

The standard and its supporting tool will be made available in multiple languages through the collaboration of the NCCs' network.

4.2.2. DOAS certification framework

Innovation

The DOAS Certification Framework represents a significant step forward in the European Diamond OA ecosystem, providing a structured and standardised mechanism to assess and recognise the compliance of INPOA publishing services with the DOAS criteria. Built on the self-assessment tool, this framework will translate the quality principles described in the DOAS into an actionable certification workflow.

The framework will introduce a multi-level compliance model around the DOAS domains, enabling publishers to demonstrate a progressive alignment with the standard.

The certification framework design will enable its implementation at the national level, ensuring its adaptation to different contexts. Multilingual accessibility will be built into the framework from the beginning, with translations of DOAS, the self-assessment tool, and the framework itself, ensuring a broader applicability.

Exploitation

Stakeholder groups

The primary stakeholder groups for the DOAS Certification Framework are:

- INPOA publishing services (OA journal publishers and in a second phase, OA book publishers), as the recipients of the certification.
- National Capacity Centres (NCCs) as main implementers at the national level. DOAS certification will enable NCCs to measure and improve the quality of local and national publishing services.
- Policymakers will be able to use DOAS certification to recognise and support quality Diamond publishing services, enabling coherent policy implementation.
- RPOs and RFOs as institutional actors.
- The Diamond OA community.

Dissemination channels

- Publication of the framework on the EDCH and the project website.
- Presentation and demonstration at Diamond OA events, conferences, and community webinars.
- Outreach campaigns through the EDCH Forum.
- Promotion via partner institutional channels: Newsletters, social media, etc
- Collaboration with aligned initiatives, for example, ALMASI, to maximise reach.
- Community engagement through NCC's network.

Partner contribution

Project partners will promote the framework within their own network and communities. DOAJ, as task lead, will coordinate this promotion, while FECYT will coordinate the translations of the DOAS and its adaptation to the self-assessment tool.

NCCs will act as the primary vehicle for national-level implementation, helping in the adoption of the framework by INPOA publishing services across Europe.

Sustainability

Maintenance

The long-term sustainability of the DOAS Certification Framework will be ensured through its integration into EDCH services, with involvement of the NCCs.

A governance framework for the DOAS and the Certification Framework will be established to ensure that both continue to evolve in line with community needs and developments in institutional publishing.

Integration

The DOAS Certification Framework will be embedded into EDCH services, as other project outputs. In the future, the framework will be positioned to serve as a European reference point for quality assessment within institutional and national OA policies across the ERA.

4.2.3. Training programme for INPOA publishing trainers including the material and certification framework

Innovation

The Training Programme and Certification Framework for INPOA publishing trainers addresses a structural need for coordinated capacity-building and professional recognition within the European Diamond OA publishing ecosystem. It will establish a structured and transferable framework for developing the competencies of OA publishing trainers through the design and delivery of dedicated training materials, learning pathways, and certification mechanisms, supported by the integration of the open source video conferencing solution BigBlueButton into the EDCH training platform.

By combining pedagogical resources, collaborative learning functionalities, and instructional design support within a single environment, the programme will significantly improve the accessibility, interoperability, efficiency, and scalability of training provision for both trainers and INPOA participants. The integration of BigBlueButton also reinforces the alignment of the training infrastructure with Diamond OA values of openness, sustainability, and community ownership. The programme will introduce a standardised methodology for onboarding, upskilling, and recognising trainers across different national and institutional contexts, while fostering collaboration and mutual learning within the INPOA community.

Exploitation

Stakeholder groups

The primary stakeholder groups for the Training Programme and Certification Framework for INPOA publishing trainers are:

- Publishers of Diamond OA journals and books.
- National Capacity Centres (NCCs), which will act as national multipliers and coordinators for trainer certification and skills development activities.
- Trainers and technical staff involved in training, who will use the programme to strengthen their training competencies.
- Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), which can support and adopt the framework within institutional publishing infrastructures.
- Policymakers seeking sustainable capacity-building solutions for Diamond OA publishing.

Dissemination channels

- Publication of the certification framework feasibility study on Zenodo, EDCH and the project website.
- Integration of training resources and tools into the EDCH Training and Resources & Guidelines services.
- Webinars, workshops, and online training sessions.
- Presentations at conferences and community meetings.
- Promotion through partner communication channels, including newsletters, websites, mailing lists, blogs and social media.
- Collaboration with European and international initiatives and infrastructures to maximise reuse and interoperability of training resources.
- Community engagement and localisation activities through the NCC network.

Partner contribution

AMU, as lead of WP3 and key tasks, will coordinate the development and integration of the training programme, certification framework, and Open Educational Resources feasibility study. OPERAS, DOAJ, OAPEN, EIFL, and other partners will contribute expertise, content development, dissemination, and community engagement activities. NCCs will support national-level adoption, translation, and implementation of training resources and certification pathways.

Partners will also contribute to the maintenance and further development of the EDCH

Training platform and the Resources & Guidelines service.

Sustainability

Maintenance

The training programme for INPOA trainers, including the material and certification framework, will be maintained in the long term through its integration into EDCH services. The NCC Network will be able to participate in the training and seek certification and hence become a federated network of trainers at the national level.

Integration

The training programme for INPOA trainers, including material, certification and BigBlueButton, will be embedded into the existing EDCH training platform. In a broader context, exploitation activities will focus on turning the training platform into a powerful tool for capacity building and community engagement.

4.2.4. DDH 2.0

Innovation

DDH 2.0 expands the Diamond Discovery Hub as a European discovery and visibility service for Diamond OA journals. Building on the first iteration developed through CRAFT-OA, DDH 2.0 improves interoperability, metadata quality, user experience, and data integration workflows, while strengthening the recognition of community-led Diamond OA publishing in Europe.

Exploitation

Stakeholder groups

The primary stakeholder groups for the DDH 2.0 will be:

- INPOA publishing services and infrastructure providers
- Libraries
- NCCs
- Researchers, and the broader OA community.

Dissemination channels

- Webinars, workshops, and online training sessions.

- Presentations at conferences and community meetings.
- Promotion through partner communication channels, including newsletters, websites, mailing lists, blogs and social media.
- Collaboration with European and international initiatives and infrastructures to maximise journal onboarding
- Community engagement through the NCC network.

Partner contribution

AEGIS-OA partners will contribute to the exploitation of DDH 2.0 through editorial support, alignment, onboarding of trusted sources and Diamond OA journals across disciplines and languages, dissemination activities, testing, validation, and supporting co-creation community engagement activities.

Sustainability

Maintenance

Technical maintenance and further development of DDH will continue through the EDCH and be managed by the leading partners for this KER - DOAJ, UGOE and ICM-UW. Editorial support, onboarding of trusted sources, and community coordination activities will continue through the DDH editorial and community network.

Integration

DDH 2.0 will be fully integrated into the EDCH service portfolio as a central infrastructure supporting visibility, interoperability, discoverability, and community coordination for Diamond OA publishing in Europe.

4.2.5. Directory of INPOA publishing professionals and framework for mobility and cooperation opportunities

Innovation

The Directory of INPOA Publishing Professionals and Framework for Mobility and Cooperation Opportunities addresses a structural gap in coordination and professional development, by combining several functions that are currently fragmented. It will create a structured directory of competences, expertise, training opportunities, mentors, mentees, and host institutions specifically dedicated to the INPOA publishing community. By integrating these elements into a shared framework, it will strengthen

visibility, discoverability, and will introduce a coordinated mechanism for identifying expertise, matching professionals with mobility and training opportunities, and supporting mutual learning. The Framework will extend the use of established mobility infrastructures, such as Erasmus+, to scholarly publishing, thus contributing to the development of skills and capacities within INPOA services.

Exploitation

Stakeholder groups

The main stakeholder groups include:

- INPOA publishing professionals seeking training and mobility opportunities
- INPOA Publishers (e.g., University Libraries, University Presses)
- University Alliances (e.g., Enlight, Guild)
- Erasmus+ offices at HEI

Dissemination channels:

- Online webinars and consultation meetings
- Presentations at events
- Promotion through the EDCH Forum, project website, and social media channels
- Outreach through partner institutions and NCC
- Engagement with university alliances and HEI networks

Partner contribution

AEGIS-OA partners will contribute to exploitation through their institutional networks and existing infrastructures. Specifically, project partners will support the mapping of competences and training opportunities within their institutions and networks, contribute as host institutions for mobility exchanges, and identify mentors and mentees. Partners holding an Erasmus Charter for Higher Education will facilitate access to Erasmus+ mobility mechanisms and provide guidance on administrative and organisational requirements. Accordingly, partners participating in university alliances can help establish strategic partnerships and integrate the framework into broader initiatives.

Sustainability

Maintenance

The sustainability of the Directory and mobility and cooperation framework will be supported through its integration within the broader EDCH ecosystem and through continued community engagement. Responsibilities are expected to be shared among participating organisations and community coordinators involved in the EDCH infrastructure. Specifically, project partners and EDCH Advocates are expected to play an important role in maintaining community engagement, updating the Directory, and coordinating future mobility activities.

A pilot phase starting in October 2026 will provide insights into the operational requirements, governance needs, and resource allocation of maintaining the framework over time. These findings will inform future sustainability planning. Long-term support will include periodic updates, continued calls for mentors and mentees, and partnerships with university alliances and Erasmus+ stakeholders.

Integration

The Directory and Framework will be designed to integrate with existing EDCH community networks, to facilitate interoperability, user engagement, and long-term adoption. In a broader context, exploitation activities will focus on the integration of the Framework into recognised European cooperation mechanisms as well as into existing institutional workflows related to staff development, training, mobility, and scholarly communication support.

4.2.6. Multi-level and multi-stakeholder framework for financial support of INPOA publishing in the ERA

Innovation

The multi-level and multi-stakeholder framework is the main output of WP6. It will be built on the existing extensive knowledge of Diamond OA funding models and financial mechanisms that have been identified and studied within the DIAMAS and ALMASI projects.

The framework will go one step forward by proposing ways to better articulate these mechanisms and to expand their adoption within European RPOs and RFOs in order to assure the sustainability of INPOA publishing activities.

The framework will put forward concrete implementation use cases and will include the active contribution of interested stakeholders in its design.

Exploitation

Stakeholder groups

The main stakeholder groups include:

- RPOs and RFOs that are already contributing or planning to contribute to the funding of INPOA publishing activities (e.g. through international bodies like Science Europe or cOAlition S)
- National and institutional policy makers (e.g. through CoNOSC)
- Intermediary stakeholders (e.g. library consortia, OBC-OJC...)
- INPOA Publishers

Dissemination channels:

- Online webinars and consultation meetings
- Presentations at events
- Promotion through existing networks: library consortia, EDCH, cOAlition S, Science Europe, ORE funders network, Diamond Action Plan
- Outreach through NCCs

Sustainability

Integration

The multi-level and multi-stakeholder framework will be useful for the future work of the ECDH Funding Task Force in order to inform and guide priorities.

5. Implementation, KPIs & Monitoring

5.1. Timeline and phases

The implementation of the Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation Plan is structured in line with the three strategic pillars of the plan (awareness raising, outreach and engagement, and exploitation) and reflects the progressive development of AEGIS-OA activities throughout the project lifecycle.

It follows an iterative approach, ensuring that communication, dissemination, engagement and exploitation activities are continuously refined and updated in response to how the project will develop and taking into consideration the ongoing feedback and input that will be received by the key stakeholder groups.

As mentioned, the communication, dissemination, outreach and exploitation plan will be implemented following the two main phases of the AEGIS-OA methodology.

During Phase 1 – Co-creation and development, activities will primarily focus on planning and setting the foundations to reach and engage with the identified AEGIS-OA stakeholder groups, community building, and awareness raising. This includes introducing the project and its objectives, activating communication channels, and supporting the early development and validation of project outputs across the different Work Packages.

During Phase 2 – Integration and implementation, activities will increasingly focus on the dissemination and uptake of results, and ultimately their long-term exploitation and sustainability. This phase will support the broader promotion and adoption of project outputs, and facilitate the integration of project tools, guidelines, recommendations and services within the EDCH.

5.2. KPIs definition and monitoring

To support the effective implementation of this Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation Plan, AEGIS-OA will monitor and assess the success and effectiveness of its activities by consulting the KPIs defined in the project proposal. The Communication and Engagement KPIs support the assessment of the visibility, reach and engagement of the stakeholder groups and will help inform the direction and development of the project outputs throughout the project lifecycle.

The KPIs described below are outlined in the project proposal and follow the Base-Target-Stretch (B-T-S) Approach.

Channel	Activity	Stakeholder Groups	KPI	Base-Target-Stretch
AEGIS-OA dedicated section on EDCH website	Main access point for the project's outputs and news	Project partners; RPOs; Scholarly societies; Libraries; INPOA publishing services RFOs; Relevant initiatives & projects; OA community; Citizens/General public	# of visitors of AEGIS-OA page	150-200-300 visits per month on average
Social media	EDCH social media (Linkedin and Bluesky)	RPOs, RFOs, Libraries, OA university presses, Scholarly societies, Relevant initiatives & projects, Citizens	# of posts/year (both LinkedIn/Blue sky)	60-80-100 posts/year on average
			# gain of followers of social media accounts during AEGIS-OA	300-500-700 followers
Communication materials	Communication material and stakeholder-specific content FAQ	RPOs, RFOs, Libraries, OA university presses, Scholarly societies, Relevant initiatives and projects,	# AEGIS related posts in Forum, tagged with "AEGIS"	3-5-7 posts/ year on average

		Publishers	# of blog posts/non-peer reviewed publications	5-10-15 blog posts/non-peer reviewed publications per year
			# of press releases	1-2-3 press releases

Table 4: KPIs for Communication activities

Channel	Activity	Stakeholder Groups	KPI	Base-Target-Stretch
Events organised by the project	Workshops / webinars organised for engagement, training and outreach purposes	INPOA publishing services; RPOs; RFOs; Libraries; OA university presses; Scholarly societies; Relevant initiatives & projects; Early career researchers	# of webinars/ workshops	15-20-25 online and in-person events in the duration of the project
			# of participants	800-1000-1200 #participants of all project-related events in total
Conferences organised by the project	Meetings to bring together project participants	All	3 conferences	1 kick-off meeting/conference, 1st online Diamond OA Festival, 1 in-person final event coinciding with the 2nd Diamond OA Festival (T1.4)
			# of participants	60-80-100 participants on average

Participation in third-party events	Participation with presentations in third-party events	RPOs, RFOs, Libraries, events organised by NCCs, OA university presses, Scholarly societies, Relevant initiatives & projects	# of third party events attended with a contribution	10-15-25 (including all WPs and stakeholder groups)
EDCH Forum	User engagement in the Forum	All	# % of DAU/MAU (Daily Active Users/Monthly Active Users) yearly average	15%-20%-25%
EDCH Forum	User gain in Forum	All	#gain of new users	200-400-600
EDCH Registry	Registry application, new organisation joining the registry	Scholarly societies, publishers, service and tools providers	#gain of registered organisations	500-600-750

Table 5: KPIs for Engagement activities

Document type	Stakeholder Groups	KPI	Base-Target-Stretch
Scientific publications to maximise and channel project outputs	RPOs, RFOs; Libraries; OA university presses; journal editors & journal staff; Scholarly societies Relevant initiatives & projects	# of publications	3-5-7 Successful submissions over the duration of the project

<p>Training materials to support capacity building in the project</p>	<p>RPOs; RFOs; Libraries; OA university presses; Scholarly societies, journal editors & journal staff; Relevant initiatives & projects</p>	<p># of training materials</p>	<p>>3 learning path descriptions (e.g., program outlines), tailored for different audiences. >5 training modules (e.g., unit within a program), including training material, reading and watching lists, possible assignments, and assessment strategies >30 training materials within the modules (e.g., lessons) in the form of presentations, written materials, and videos >Recordings of online events organised by the project, promotional videos etc. that will be available via YouTube</p>
<p>Guidelines and recommendations</p>	<p>RPOs; RFOs; Libraries; University presses; Scholarly societies; Journal editors & journal staff; Relevant initiatives & projects</p>	<p># of guidelines & recommendations</p>	<p>Set of recommendations and guidelines for RFOs, RPOs (in particular libraries), and policy makers including a specific set of guidelines for OA books and journals. New resources & guidelines for book publishers, availability of these articles and guidelines for book publishers in Portuguese, Croatian and Spanish</p>

Table 6: KPIs for Publications and guidelines

To keep track of KPI progress, a monitoring tracking sheet has been created to be used internally by all partners to document all communication, dissemination, outreach and exploitation efforts.

AEGIS-OA		INSTRUCTIONS ON HOW TO FILL IN THE TRACKER		
Welcome to the AEGIS-OA Communication, Dissemination & Outreach tracker. These tabs will be used to collect information on all communication, dissemination and outreach activities from AEGIS-OA, which will be reported to the European Commission via the portal and for the periodic and final reporting.				
Please find below the instructions on WHAT and HOW to fill in the several tabs.				
TAB INSTRUCTIONS				
1. Publications				
WHO SHOULD FILL: all partners				
WHAT INFO: please indicate here all the scientific publications you published related to AEGIS-OA				
2. Dissemination Activities				
WHO SHOULD FILL: all partners				
WHAT INFO: please indicate here all the activities you prepared to reach the target audience, that is, any potential user of the project results. (see Useful info tab)				
3. Communication Activities				
WHO SHOULD FILL: all partners				
WHAT INFO: please indicate here all the activities you prepared to reach a wide audience. Please note communication activities are not just aimed to reach potential end-users, but the general audience, including media and general public. (see Useful info tab)				
4. Events				
WHO SHOULD FILL: all partners				
WHAT INFO: please indicate here all the events you organised (e.g. conference, workshops, focus group, webinars etc) and also all the 3rd party events where the project had visibility or participation (e.g. poster, exhibition stand, lightning talk, panel discussion, presentation, paper submission etc)				
5. KPIS				
WP1 (Comms group) to fill it in				

Figure 3: Screenshot of the AEGIS-OA Communication, Dissemination & Outreach tracker monitoring sheet.

6. Risk management

6.1. Identified risks

For the successful implementation of the Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation plan, the following potential critical risks that might affect the overall success of AEGIS-OA and the implementation of this plan are identified.

6.1.1. Branding Confusion

The AEGIS-OA brand and visual identity were created to be purposefully aligned with the EDCH brand in order to establish from the early start of the project the connection with the EDCH and to pave the way for the seamless integration of the project results within the EDCH after the project's end. While the branding alignment offers clear benefits, there is a potential risk of confusion between project-specific activities and broader EDCH services and initiatives. In addition, the inconsistent use of visual identity, branding, or messaging across consortium communication channels could reduce the visibility and recognition of the project and its results.

6.1.2. Lack of adoption of project outputs by the community

While all project outputs and activities are designed to support, motivate and propel Diamond OA forward, there is a risk that some stakeholders may have limited capacity, time, or resources to engage with and adopt the project outputs, tools, and services developed within AEGIS-OA. This might be the case depending on the level of Diamond OA adoption or the maturity of the different stakeholder groups and their capacity to contextualise and adopt the solutions created.

In addition, outputs may face lower uptake if they are perceived as too complex, insufficiently aligned with stakeholder needs, or disconnected from existing workflows and practices when translated into national contexts.

6.2. Mitigation strategies

To address the risks identified above, AEGIS-OA developed mitigation strategies to minimise and absorb any potential barriers to the successful implementation of the plan.

To reduce the risk of branding confusion with the EDCH, AEGIS-OA created a clear and consistent communication approach across all project activities and channels that is

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outlined in this plan. The Communication Kit (see Appendix A) developed within the project provides detailed branding guidelines, templates, and messaging recommendations for all consortium partners to ensure alignment across channels and the coherent presentation of project activities and results. Communication activities and messaging, including project materials and presentations, will also clearly position AEGIS-OA as a project that is integrated within the EDCH while ensuring appropriate visibility of the project identity and results.

To support the uptake and adoption of project outputs, AEGIS-OA adopts a community-oriented and stakeholder-driven approach across all Work Packages as outlined in this plan. Stakeholders will be involved throughout the project lifecycle via consultations, co-creation activities, pilot actions, training activities, and community engagement initiatives. Stakeholder engagement will also be assessed continuously throughout the project's lifecycle in consultation with WP leaders and via assessing the established monitoring lists and adjustments to this plan will be made in good time in case low engagement is observed.

In particular, working closely with the NCCs and focusing on building and nurturing these national hubs will ensure that the AEGIS-OA activities and results are relevant, adaptable and can be used across disciplines and borders.

Finally, the integration of outputs into EDCH services and activities will further support their visibility, usability, and long-term sustainability beyond the project lifetime.

7. Conclusion & next steps

The Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation plan presented establishes the initial strategic actions for communication, engagement, dissemination, and exploitation activities within AEGIS-OA. As the project progresses, the activities and approaches described in this document will continue to evolve in line with stakeholder feedback, project developments, and the maturation of project outputs across the different Work Packages. This document is envisioned as a living document and it will be regularly updated and revisited depending on performance that will be tracked via the monitoring mechanisms.

7.1. Immediate next actions

The immediate next actions following the delivery of D1.3 include:

- Creation of a stakeholder channels database to fully mobilise partner and external networks to promote AEGIS-OA
- Further enrichment of the Communications Kit with project materials
- Kicking off initial communications and outreach activities across the key identified stakeholder groups
- Coordination with all AEGIS-OA WPs to ensure the relevance and alignment of communications, dissemination and engagement activities
- Coordination with all AEGIS-OA WPs to support the upcoming AEGIS-OA organised events
- Further enrichment of the relevant external events and alignment initiatives

Particular attention during the initial implementation phase will be placed on strengthening collaboration with the NCC network and ensuring broad stakeholder participation across different national and institutional contexts.

7.2. Link to D1.5 update

This deliverable presents the initial version of the AEGIS-OA Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation plan will be updated during the project lifecycle through Deliverable D1.5 which will be presented towards the end of the project.

The D1.5 update will present the updated version of this plan in the form of the report, gathering input through the AEGIS-OA outputs, activities, stakeholder feedback and lessons learned during the implementation of the project. It will report on the

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communication, dissemination, outreach and exploitation activities and any adjustments to priorities, messaging and channels where relevant.

The update will also reflect the maturity and integration of project outputs into the EDCH, supporting the long-term sustainability and impact of AEGIS-0A results beyond the duration of the project.

Appendices

Appendix A: The AEGIS-0A Communications Kit

AEGIS-0A Logo

Figure 4: AEGIS-0A Logo

Social media cards

Figure 5: Social media cards example

Presentation templates

Figure 6: Presentation template example

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Brand Guidelines

Figure 7: The AEGIS-0A Brand Guidelines²⁵

²⁵

<https://edch.eu/sites/default/files/AEGIS-0A/Brand%20Guidelines/AEGIS-0A%20Brand%20Guidelines.pdf>